

Approach for Passive Safety Assessment of Rearward-Sitting Occupants

Ömer Dönmez¹, Ricardo Tejero de la Piedra², Simona Klose¹, Matthieu Riolet², Lukas Rozek¹, Ondřej Vaculín¹ and Christian Hach²

Abstract—The introduction of highly automated vehicles (HAVs) will allow vehicle occupants to take advantage of new seating configurations, such as sitting rearward in the first row. One critical aspect of assessing occupant safety during high-speed impacts is the lack of a dedicated safety framework for rearward-facing passengers in the first row. This paper introduces a method to develop new assessment criteria for these novel seat configurations. Thus, this research presents some preliminary results of rearward-facing occupant injury biomechanics analyses carried out employing a variety of anthropomorphic test devices (ATDs) and the VIVA+ 50M human body model (HBM), restrained with different belt configurations and considering different seat typologies. It reviews the suitability of 50th percentile male ATDs to capture a biofidelic engagement with the seat structure and belt system and evaluates the reaction loads on the occupant, along with the energy management resulting from seat back rotational stiffness and energy-absorbing foams layered behind the seat cushion. Based on the results, the THOR-AV-50M is a suitable candidate for further biofidelity analysis. Torso occupant loads can be effectively reduced utilizing seat back rotation but pelvis load management requires further studies.

Index Terms—anthropometric test device, crash test, human body model, passive vehicle safety, rearward-sitting occupant, simulation.

I. INTRODUCTION

In Europe, vehicles are divided into several categories according to the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UN ECE) regulations, which determine the requirements for their approval. Passenger cars are classified under category M1. The regulations stipulated for this category mandate the conducting of frontal and side crash tests. The objective of these tests is to ensure the safety of vehicle occupants in the event of a traffic accident.

These assessment procedures focus only on forward-facing occupants. Nevertheless, the emergence of automated vehicles is set to facilitate novel seating arrangements for occupants, including rear-facing positions within the first row. The most significant change in the assessment of crash tests with rearward-sitting occupants are the frontal crash configurations in which the accelerations on the occupant have opposite orientations.

Current regulations define biomechanical pass/fail criteria for the Offset Deformable Barrier (ODB) at 56 km/h and

This research has been performed in the AWARE2ALL project, which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 861570 (Research and Innovation Action)

¹CARISSMA - Inst. of Safety in Future Mobility, Technische Hochschule Ingolstadt, Ingolstadt, Germany oemer.doenmez@carissma.eu

²CAE Engineering, Humanetics Europe GmbH, Heidelberg, Germany

Full Width Rigid Barrier (FWRB) crash tests at 50 km/h in accordance with UN ECE R 94 and R 137 respectively. Due to different biomechanical loads on the occupants a new assessment approach should be defined, which would extend current regulations to include rearward-facing passengers.

Another issue concerns the suitability of existing ATDs for rearward-facing configurations. The regulations mentioned above use the 5th percentile female and 50th percentile male from the Hybrid III family. These ATDs have been developed specifically to assess biomechanical loads in the event of a frontal crash. As mentioned previously, the new orientation of the acceleration vector results in different loads, so the situation can be considered similar to whiplash testing performed by consumer testing organizations such as EuroNCAP, which use the BIORID2 dummy. BIORID2 was specifically developed for low speed and therefore its biofidelity and robustness is limited to 24 km/h.

The systematic analysis of possible crash assessment methods for rearward-sitting occupants in the first row is part of the research that is being carried out in the EC funded AWARE2ALL project¹. The project focuses on safety systems and human-machine interfaces oriented to a diverse population towards future scenarios with highly automated vehicles.

Thus, this paper presents an approach to develop new assessment criteria for rearward-facing seat configurations. After the state-of-the-art in Section II, Section III focuses on the scenario description. Section IV describes the simulation model used for this research and Section V presents some preliminary simulation results. The paper is concluded in Section VI.

II. STATE-OF-THE-ART

The assessment of rear impacts has focused particularly on whiplash testing at low speeds. Another special case was rearward-facing child seats. However, the advent of automated driving vehicles now enables rearward-facing seating for adult occupants in high-speed crash scenarios. The limited prevalence of severe injuries from high-speed rear impacts explains the absence of a dedicated global safety assessment framework for these conditions in both regulatory type approval and consumer rating systems.

The following sections review the current situation from three perspectives: the applicability of existing anthropometric test devices (ATDs), insights from moderate-speed rear impact studies on current automotive seats, and specific

¹www.aware2all.eu

injury biomechanics research involving post-mortem human subjects (PMHS) for rearward-facing occupants.

A. Human surrogates

No anthropometric test device (ATD) has been developed specifically for high-speed rear impact of collision. While rear-impact ATDs such as BioRID2 and EvaRID offer a more detailed representation of the spine, their design and scope of biofidelity limit them to speeds up to 24 km/h (whiplash conditions).

Although the Hybrid-III 50th percentile ATD was designed in the 1970s for high-speed frontal impacts, it is used in rear-impact safety assessments for low speed seat regulations in the USA (FMVSS 202a). It also serves as a ballast dummy in seat integrity evaluations, particularly in federal fuel system integrity and electrolyte spillage tests (FMVSS 301R [1] and FMVSS 305 [2]). However, no injury criteria are specified for ATD performance in these applications.

B. Seat typologies and injury outcomes

1) *Free-standing supported commercial automotive seats subjected to moderate speed rear impacts:* Edwards et al. [3] from the Insurance Institute for Highway Safety (IIHS) studied rear-impact passenger safety by collecting FMVSS301R pulse data from automotive manufacturers and conducting a large-scale sled test campaign with seats from US vehicles produced between 2012 and 2019. Ragland et al. [4] reported that vehicle damage in FMVSS301R tests is comparable to survivable rear-impact crashes. Following the test procedure, a Hybrid-III 50th percentile ATD was positioned on the seat, and belt pretensioners were activated using OEM-specific vehicle data. Driver seat back deflection and dynamic pressure distribution were measured, with maximum seat back rotation clustering around an average of 25°.

2) *Rigidly supported commercial automotive seats subjected to high speed rear impacts:* Between 2021 and 2022, PMHS and ATD experimental tests were executed by Hagedorn et. al ([5], [6]), and Wang et al. [7] for the National Highway Traffic Safety Administration (NHTSA). These sled tests used commercially available seats and sustained decelerations with a Δv of 56 km/h, representing crash test pulses from the US regulation FMVSS208. The seats were selected due to their specific restraint and structural features among cars popularly driven in the US (Honda Accord, Honda Odyssey).

In preliminary tests with seats occupied by a Hybrid-III 50th percentile, the hardware seats exhibited structural failure. To address this, an additional load-cell-instrumented support structure was added. Subsequent tests were conducted using PMHS, the H-III 50th male, THOR-50M, and THOR-AV-50M.

The rib fracture results, particularly for the Odyssey seat, demonstrated a strong relationship between rib fracture locations and the design and packaging of seat back frames. The PMHS recorded HIC15 values ranging from 892 to 4147, with no skull fractures observed. Given this and prior studies showing that skull fracture sensitivity depends on impact

location, Kang [8] questioned whether HIC limits and risk curves developed for frontal impact standards are applicable to rear-impact scenarios without further research.

3) *Homogeneous surface seat bench subjected to high speed rear impacts:* Based on learnings from the commercial seat campaign, Kang et al. at Ohio State University [9], funded by the Research Consortium for Crashworthiness in Automated Driving Systems (RCCADS) [10], designed and tested a research prototype seat back. The seat had a homogeneous, upright surface (25° angle) intended to reduce injury risk by eliminating indentation points or stress concentrators on the passenger’s back. To compensate for the lack of energy absorption (EA) in the rigid structure, a 40 mm EA foam layer (PE Plastazote MP15FR [11]) was placed between the comfort foam and the flat seat back panel. The headrest included a 90 mm EA foam layer, and a padded low leg catcher with 50 mm of EA foam provided an additional lower load path. The seat was instrumented with load cells to measure reaction forces between occupants and fixture. PMHS posture and the applied crash pulse were consistent with the previous supported seat test campaign by Kang. Results, summarized in Table I, showed that two of three PMHS sustained severe ribcage fractures and all sustained pelvis fractures. The study identified and analyzed novel rear-facing injury mechanisms and suggested potential predictors of injury severity to reduce the Maximum Abbreviated Injury Scale (MAIS) score.

TABLE I
RCCADS HOMOGENEOUS SEAT BACK. PMHS INJURY CLASSIFICATION AND SEAT BACK LOADS. KANG ET AL. 2025 [9].

	Thorax + Lumbar Region		Pelvis Region	
	MAIS	Reaction Force (kN)	MAIS	Reaction Force (kN)
PMHS1	5	34.4	3	18.9
PMHS2	0	26.2	3	17.8
PMHS3	3	29.5	3	14.6
Average		30.0		17.1

III. SCENARIO DESCRIPTION

As introduced in the previous section, the aim of this research is to find a way to assess the passive safety of rearward traveling passengers in the first row. Based on existing testing procedures, a Full Frontal Rigid-Wall load-case with a maximum impact velocity of 40 km/h has been selected for the upcoming investigations within this research. The selection of the relevant load case is based on the following considerations:

a) *How to approve M1 vehicles?:* According to the EU regulation 2018/858, M1 category vehicles are being approved using high-speed frontal (UN ECE Regulation No. 94 and 137) and side (UN ECE Regulation No. 95 and 135) crash tests. For rearward-facing passengers in the first row, side-impact events are expected to produce only minimal differences in body loading compared with forward-facing passengers.

b) Which impact velocity can be expected for people movers?: People movers are usually used to transport passengers in inner-city environments where the permitted speed is 50 km/h. The Car-to-Car Front Head-On Straight (CCFhos) test procedure defined by EuroNCAP describes a test for the autonomous emergency braking (AEB) system in vehicles. This test awards the maximum rating if the ego-vehicle can reduce its initial velocity (50 km/h) by 20 km/h. Under this assumption, the ego-vehicle would collide with the oncoming vehicle traveling at 50 km/h. Assuming a similar vehicle design and weight, the equivalent impact velocity against a rigid barrier would be 40 km/h.

IV. SIMULATION MODEL

A. Occupant Model

Selecting the appropriate occupant surrogate is essential for achieving realistic and biofidelic simulation results, both in hardware testing and numerical simulation. Fig. 1 and Table II summarize the chosen surrogates (ATDs and HBM), outlining their limitations and the expected benefits of including them in the validation of passive safety technologies.

Fig. 1. Overview of occupant surrogates considered for high speed rear impact assessment in this paper

B. Vehicle Interior

As part of the AWARE2ALL project, DLR developed an autonomous M1 shuttle prototype with a novel so-called "campfire" seating configuration, in which occupants in the first row face the opposite direction to the forward driving direction, while those in the second row face the forward driving direction.

C. Seat

The RCCADS virtual seat FE-model (Fig. 2) was built from the ground up based on the same publicly available CAD data from [9] used by RCCADS to build the hardware sled.

1) *RCCADS Seat bench modeling*: As shown in Fig. 2, the homogeneous RCCADS seat has four main characteristics:

The seat structure consists of a flat seat back steel plate. In this sense, the RCCADS seat structure differs from usual car seats, which consist of a frame and a thin closing back plate, on which the different seat components are mounted, resulting in a non-homogeneous, locally protruding structure, exposed to the occupant's back and potentially harmful during high speed rear impact [8].

The structure is rigidly supported to the sled by a fixture, representing a seat bench integrated in a stiffened sled vehicle

Fig. 2. FE-model of the supported homogeneous flat RCCADS seat.

structure. This is modeled with rigid elements, except for the load cells.

Since the seat back plate is rigidly connected to the fixture through the load cells, a 40mm layer of energy absorbing foam is solely responsible for the energy management. The foam is modeled using 20mm size, fully integrated, selective reduced hexa element formulation.

The belt system: a three point belt system, consisting of a retractor pretensioner and low friction D-ring, both mounted to the sled fixture at the height of the occupant's shoulder. Buckle and anchor are attached to the fixture. No lap pretensioner is used. During the occupant ramping phase, the belt can slide back from the lap portion to the torso portion, i.e. no crash locking tongue is used. The seatbelt retractor pretensioner is triggered at 10ms.

2) *Foam material selection*: The publication cites the foam material used in hardware, but no mechanical properties are provided. Material foam data for FE-explicit simulations is expensive to generate: hardware samples in different sizes and specifically cut and conditioned are required. Material coupon testing involves several loading modes (tension, compression, shear) at quasistatic and high strain rate speeds, as well as component testing (drop tower tests on samples sized similarly to final system application). Unfortunately, hardware material testing, mechanical property characterization, and FE-solver coding were not the scope of this project. As replacement, this study involved extensive literature research and numerically benchmarking several publicly available foam material cards for LS-DYNA. Finally, the comfort foam and an impact foam from the OpenVT platform (Toyota Auris) [12] are adopted in the RCCADS FE seat model for the comfort foam (seat back) and Energy Absorption Foam (cross-linked polyethylene - PXL), since they display similar mechanical responses as the hardware from RCCADS (PE Foam).

3) *Transforming the supported RCCADS bench into a unsupported free standing seat back model to study deflection based energy management*: Free standing or partially supported seats absorb energy by bending and/or rotating around the recliner axis, hence utilizing available deformation space in the vehicle [3]. To simulate the contribution of the seat back deflection and recliner mechanism torsion, the fixture

TABLE II
OCCUPANT 50TH MALE FE-MODELS CONSIDERED FOR HIGH-SPEED REARWARD-FACING IMPACT

Occupant	General Purpose	CAE Version	Application
H-III 50th Male	High Speed Front and "ballast" for seat integrity testing. FMVSS202a low speed rear	HH V1.7.2	Hardware ATD most commonly available in test labs and used in regulations. Monolithic thoracic spine and straight neck. Used in research as baseline and determining seat loads.
THOR-50M	High Speed Front	US V1.9.2	Next Generation ATD. 4 Point chest deformation measurement in X and Z. Two rubber spine blocks for increased torso bending biofidelity. Acetabulum load cells to measure axial forces acting on pelvis. Customized with H-III legs.
THOR-AV-50M	High Speed Front with adaptations for recline seating and rear impact	V1.0	Modified US THOR-50M for Autonomous Vehicles. Re-designed abdominal parts. Curved neck geometry for improved positioning with respect to head rest.
VIVA+ 50M	Human Body Model developed within EU OpenVT Project.	V2.0.0	Correlated with male and female PMHS data for low speed rear impact (16 km/h, 25 km/h). Not correlated with PMHS high speed rear impact data.

behind the seat back (frame and load cells) is removed and a rotational hinge or pivot is mounted between the seat back and the seat pan structure (yellow triangle in Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. RCCADS rotating seat with D-ring and belt retractor mounted on fixture (left) and mounted on seat back (right). Belt anchorages to fixture represented as line pattern.

Since the load cells are removed together with the supported fixture, the reaction loads on the occupant are extracted from the FE contact definition, referring to a local coordinate system attached to the seat back plate, which provides force components (normal and tangential) with respect to the seat back angle over time. In previous studies allowing seat back rotation on a generic seat [13], the torque-rotation characteristic at the pivot was controlled by means of seatbelt webbing wrapped around the seat back structure. The pivot rotational stiffness is modeled using an idealized linear torsional spring that only allows seat back rotation around the horizontal bottom edge (Y-axis) and constrains all other degrees of freedom. Recliner stiffness data are intellectual property of seat mechanism suppliers and have to be reverse-engineered via hardware testing or calculation. In order to determine a realistic magnitude, the rotational stiffness was iteratively adjusted to finally match a 25° dynamic seat deflection, replicating the test conditions from [3] (belted H-III 50th Male ATD, average FMVSS301 pulse).

The resulting stiffness of 165 Nm/deg is assumed to be linear and no collapse of the recliner mechanism is considered. Compared to the recliner stiffness of 115 Nm/deg estimated via testing by Ngo et al. [14] for the Odyssey seat, this value would require a high strength, double side recliner or purposely designed system to achieve this level

of retention without mechanical failure.

The reaction forces between the dummy and the seat back (Fig. 4) for the thorax, lumbar and pelvis area, as well as the complete seat back, were extracted and compared with a seat with a low ratio of claims in the field (Edwards et al. [3]). These values will be used as a force based threshold approximation for a non injurious performance.

Fig. 4. Occupant load instrumentation via Load Cells (Blue) and Contact Forces (Red)

4) *Location of the seat belt anchorages for the unsupported pivoting seat:* Belt anchorages can be located either at the vehicle structure or mounted on the seat structure (known as ABTS- All Belts to Seat, or IBS- Integrated Belt to Seat). Mounting the retractor on the seat greatly influences the occupant kinematics by improving occupant retention on seat, but they can also induce potentially injurious vertical loads on the occupant spine. In order to capture these effects, two versions of the pivoting homogeneous seat were modeled: one with the retractor and D-ring mounted on the vehicle fixture (same location as baseline RCCADS seat) and one in which retractor and D-ring are mounted on the seat structure and rotate together with it, enabling a constant relative position of the D-ring to the seat back as shown in Fig. 3.

D. Crash Pulse

For the baseline assessment, the vehicle crash pulse applied to the sled was generated for a vehicle collision speed

of 40 km/h against a rigid wall as described in Section III. The pulse was extracted from a full-frontal crash simulation of DLRs People Mover, characterized by a Δv 43.5 km/h, OLC 25.6 g, and peak acceleration 49 g. The acceleration pulse obtained from the shuttle prototype crash test at 40 km/h is compared to the 56 km/h NHTSA (Kang studies [8], [9]) and 36 km/h FMVSS 301 pulses (Edwards study [3]) in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Rear impact pulse comparison - AWARE2ALL 40 km/h full frontal crash test

E. Occupant Positioning

The ATDs and the VIVA+ 50th Male HBM [15] were positioned according to Kang et al. [8], [9] (see Fig. 6). The H-point of the H-III 50M in hardware tests served as the reference for FE positioning. Both ATD and HBM lumbar regions contacted or slightly compressed the seatback foam. H-III pelvis vertical position was estimated using gravity settling, resulting in an H-point offset of 135 mm from the seat back foam plane (longitudinal) and 87 mm above the seat cushion plane (vertical). THOR-50M and THOR-AV-50M H-points were derived as offsets from the H-III per Euro NCAP MPDB protocol, while the VIVA+ 50M pelvis position was obtained via gravity settling. For THOR-50M, head level alignment could not be achieved simultaneously with head backset and pelvis/torso tilt tolerances.

Fig. 6. H-III 50th Male FE-Model position on RCCADS CAE Seat

V. SIMULATION RESULTS

The simulations were carried out using the explicit FE code LS-DYNA R12.2.1. The time step was set by the occupant models: 0.6 μs for the H-III 50th Male, THOR-50M and THOR-AV-50M ATD Models and 0.3 μs for the VIVA+ 50M HBM (as indicated in the HBM model documentation).

The CAE results are reviewed according to following criteria:

- Seat back deflection: excessive seat back deflections can exceed the available deformation space and promote occupant ejection or contact with hazardous parts;
- Reaction forces of the seat on the occupant, since no biomechanical thresholds are available for high-speed rear impact events;
- Occupant kinematics: particularly of neck and spine, will be compared using the VIVA+ 50M HBM as reference.

A. Results of the unsupported homogeneous seat with rotational pivot

Using the H-III 50th Male on the integrated seatbelt configuration as baseline and replacing the IIHS Pulse by the AWARE2ALL pulse, the seat back deflection increases from 25° to 35°. Also as result of the pulse change, the pelvic load severely increased from 6 kN (Fig. 7) to 27 kN (Fig. 8), while thoracic and lumbar reaction forces moderately increased from 6 kN to 8.7 kN.

Fig. 7. Distribution of occupant loads for H-III 50th on rotational IBS Seat with FMVSS301 rear impact pulse (image at max seat back deflection, 25 deg).

The 27 kN force recorded in the pelvic region exceeded by 58 % the 17.1 kN measured at the bottom load cells in Kang et al. [16] RCCADS PMHS testing (see Table I), which resulted in consistent pelvic fractures across all three specimens and would be considered highly injurious. These findings indicate the need for dedicated countermeasures to mitigate pelvic fracture risk. In this configuration, a 35° seat back rotation implies a longitudinal excursion of the headrest of 517 mm, within which the occupant must ideally be protected from contacting stiff vehicle structures. This deformation space is not only far larger in the AWARE2ALL People Mover Vehicle, but is further reduced by intrusions from the front-end structure moving in the opposite direction, potentially increasing the loads acting on the occupant as indicated in Fig. 9.

Fig. 8. Reaction forces acting on the occupants for an homogeneous flat pivoting vs supported seat back

Fig. 9. Potential interaction seat and occupant to vehicle structure at time of max. seat back deflection (overlay)

In terms of ATD kinematics, both THOR-50M and THOR-AV-50M demonstrated behavior comparable to the HBM in neck flexion, spine extension, and pelvis rotation. In contrast, the H-III exhibited substantially lower pelvic rotation, primarily due to its stiff coupling with the lap belt. For the H-III, relative motion between the torso and pelvis was concentrated at the rubber spine joint rather than being distributed along the spine. THOR-AV-50M offers several advantages over THOR-50M regarding belt-coupling biofidelity. These improvements are attributed to its extended pelvis geometry, optimized for reclined postures, which provides a stable lap belt contact surface during ramping. Additionally, the THOR-AV pelvis stiffness ensures full engagement with the pelvis flesh without excessively constraining vertical motion, avoiding the limitations associated with a stiff pelvic flesh developed for front impact biofidelity of the H-III 50th male as presented in Fig. 10.

Finally, differences were observed in abdominal package behavior: the H-III abdominal insert moved freely between the pelvis and torso flesh, whereas the THOR was constrained by the IR-TRACCS system. The THOR-AV achieved a more distributed deformation pattern beneath the jacket, indicating improved anatomical realism.

Effect of D-ring Location: Simulations revealed that integrating D-rings and pretensioners into the body-in-white (BIW) structure prevented the belt engaging on the shoulder, resulting in greater vertical pelvic displacement, increased occupant ramping, and more pronounced seat back deflection, thereby expanding the required energy absorption zone.

B. Results of the supported homogeneous seat

Preventing seat back deflection by stiffening and integrating the seat in the BIW while relying solely on a 40 mm layer of energy-absorbing leads to a significant increase in upper-body reaction loads, from 7 kN to 28 kN. This value lies within the range of the injurious 30 kN force measured in the PMHS tests presented by [16] (see Table I). Although the foam selection has not yet undergone any optimization, these findings underscore the complexity of balancing on-seat energy management and the energy dissipation provided through the rotational stroke, particularly when considering the clearance available in vehicles. Due to the higher loads measured in the pivot location and associated to pelvis fractures, a combination of fuse energy absorption elements to preserve the integrity of the recliner mechanism while reducing the pelvis loads are necessary.

The H-III 50th Male ATD again exhibited a relatively stiff response in the neck, torso, and pelvis regions, with torso extension concentrated in the lumbar rubber element. Unlike THOR-50M and THOR-AV-50M, the H-III lacks dedicated pelvic instrumentation (e.g., acetabulum load cells) that could capture the “open-book” pelvic injury mechanism reported by Kang et al. [17]. Both THOR variants feature a more compliant ribcage capable of representing inertial loading and measuring rib rotation associated with ramping—an injury mechanism also postulated by Kang.

Additional advantages of the THOR-AV include a neck design that promotes a more natural posture relative to the headrest [18], eliminates vulnerable sensor cabling, and replaces IR-TRACCS with abdominal pressure sensors (APTS). Fig. 11 illustrates the neck interaction with the headrest foam. Although validated only for low-speed rear impacts, the VIVA+ 50M model demonstrates a more realistic and evenly distributed neck deformation pattern within the foam compared to the ATDs.

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND OPEN PROBLEMS

This study presents rearward-facing occupant injury biomechanics analyses, conducted using the explicit FE code LS-DYNA, employing a variety of anthropomorphic test devices and the VIVA+ 50M human body model. Two different seat typologies (fixed bench vs free-standing) are considered. For the free-standing or pivoting seat back, two different belt configurations (vehicle mounted vs seat mounted) are studied. The baseline deceleration applied to the sled model was extracted from a People Mover Vehicle (DLR) full-frontal crash finite element simulation at 40 km/h impact velocity.

The seat FE-model was built based on the RCCADS homogeneous seat back concept, replicating the reinforced

Fig. 10. Coupling between lap belt and pelvis flesh. Abdomen package displacement. H-III (left), THOR-50M (left-mid), THOR-AV-50M (right mid), VIVA+50M (right)

Fig. 11. Position of the head relative to headrest at time 0ms (upper row) and neck deformed shape at time of max coupling (bottom row). H-III 50th Male left, THOR-50M left-mid, THOR-AV-50M right mid, VIVA+ 50M right

structure representative of a seat bench integrated into the BIW with a layer of energy absorption foam. In a second step, the structure was modified by removing the support and introducing a pivot to allow seat back rotation about the lower seat edge. The rotational stiffness of the pivot was tuned to represent the average seat back deflection (25°) observed in the FMVSS 301 rear-impact sled test campaign by Edwards et al. [3], using an H-III 50th Male ATD.

One aspect of this study approaches qualitatively the suitability of 50th percentile male ATDs (H-III 50th Male, THOR-50M, THOR-AV-50M) and HBM (VIVA+ 50M) to represent biofidelic occupant kinematics and human like engagement with the seat structure and restraint system. The THOR-AV-50M delivers the more biofidelic ATD kinematics (neck flexion, abdomen content, pelvis engagement to lap belt), followed by the THOR-M50, with a less suitable neck design for head rest positioning and interaction. Further ATD design refinement might be required to ensure repeatability and robustness. The VIVA+ 50M HBM detailed neck model showed the most realistic neck bending during the ramping (pivoting seat) and interaction with the headrest (fixed seat). The injury biofidelity of VIVA+ 50M has not yet been validated for high speed rear impact. The H-III 50M showed

an overly stiff response (neck, spine, pelvis), which is more apparent with increasing seat back deflection.

To determine the potential injurious conditions of the pulse and restraint configuration, the reaction forces between seat and occupant were evaluated, along with the energy management resulting from seat back rotational stiffness and EA foam layer. All three ATDs tended to deliver similar force levels, with the H-III ranging in the higher side. Using the occupant loads as a coarse predictor of the injury risk, both seat configurations caused pelvis loads above known fracture levels. The pivoting seat mitigated very effectively the torso loads, but the seat back rotation increased by 10 degrees, which highly increases the risk of interaction of occupant to the intruding front vehicle structure. Completely constraining the seat back rotation and managing the energy with a 40mm layer of PE foam was clearly insufficient and raised the forces above associated MAIS3+ injurious thresholds.

In terms of seat design, the reported benefit observed with the Homogeneous Flat Pivoting Seat is based on the reduction of the thorax and lumbar forces, which shall mitigate posterior rib fractures. However, the actual rib fracture injury mechanism, as described by Kang, is more complex and might be exacerbated by excessive occupant ramping and

abdominal content displacement. A more exhaustive analysis of ribcage deformation under progressively increasing seatback angles is required to better understand and mitigate rib fracture mechanisms. Pelvis fractures remain an issue and would require dedicated investigations.

The present study has limited the ATD biofidelity assessment to a qualitative evaluation of occupant kinematics and coupling to the seat. In future work within the AWARE2ALL project, the biofidelity of the different ATD and HBM models will be addressed quantitatively, through comparison of occupant signals and injury curves with hardware test data. Such analyses are essential to verify both the biomechanical validity of occupant surrogates and their numerical predictive capabilities. However, this analysis requires a specific characterization of the seat FE-model, particularly the recliner mechanism and its mounting brackets. Publicly available FE seat models are not yet sufficiently correlated for computing high-severity rear impacts and require significant refinement to serve as predictive tools. Ongoing efforts by NHTSA to revise FMVSS207 [19] include investments in seat characterization and occupied seat sled testing, aiming to address this gap. Similar initiatives are needed to develop and validate seat models that accurately reflect the design and materials typical of European vehicle cockpits. Moreover, additional experimental injury biomechanics testing is required to increase the statistical significance of the PMHS data collected to date and to extend coverage to female and obese occupants.

Finally, regulatory front impact load cases involving barrier offset (UN ECE R94) that add oblique occupant loading and different pulse characteristics need to be addressed. The specific 40 km/h full-frontal pulse used herein, from the AWARE2ALL project, may not represent other vehicles. The high g-peak at a moderate Δv reflects the difficulty from reduced crush space due to shorter front overhangs and occupant interaction risks with intruding structures. Furthermore, regulations on seat and child restraint safety (e.g., UN ECE R17, R21, R129) may require revision to address novel seating configurations and emerging injury risks.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors would like to acknowledge the kind support of Andrew Harrison from DLR, who designed the vehicle and its simulation model. The authors also highly appreciate Pierre Culiere from ESI Group and Daniel Riemensperger from Humanetics Europe for the consultations on the crash test configuration. Furthermore, the authors gratefully acknowledge the support of Prof. Yun-Seok Kang from The Ohio State University.

REFERENCES

- [1] U.S. Department of Transportation National Highway Traffic Safety Administration "Laboratory Test Procedure For FMVSS 301R Fuel System Integrity – Rear Impact," TP-301R-02, January 17, 2007.
- [2] U.S. Department of Transportation National Highway Traffic Safety Administration "Laboratory Test Procedure For FMVSS 305, Electric Powered Vehicles: Electrolyte Spillage and Electrical Shock Protection." TP-305-02, May 24, 2022.

- [3] M.A. Edwards, M.L. Brumbelow, R.E. Trempe and T.C. Gorjanc, "Seat Design Characteristics Affecting Occupant Safety in Low- and High-Severity Rear-Impact Collisions," in IRCOBI Conference 2019, Florence, Italy, IRC-19-11, pp 13–31.
- [4] C.L. Ragland, "Research tests to develop improved FMVSS 301 rear impact test procedure," in 16th ESV conference 1998, Windsor, Ontario, Canada, 98-S4-P-16, pp 907–910.
- [5] A. Hagedorn, "Biofidelity Assessment of THOR-50M and H3 50th ATDs in Rear-Facing Rigid Seat Tests", 1st Annual RCCADS Workshop, May 26, 2021.
- [6] A. Hagedorn, J. Stammen, R. Ramachandra, H. Rhule et al., "Biofidelity Evaluation of THOR-50M in Rear-Facing Seating Configurations Using an Updated Biofidelity Ranking System," SAE Int. J. Trans. Safety 10(2):291–375, 2022 doi:10.4271/09-10-02-0013.
- [7] Z.J. Wang, "Biomechanical Responses of the THOR-AV ATD in Rear Facing Test Conditions," SAE Technical Paper 2022-01-0836, 2022, doi:10.4271/2022-01-0836.
- [8] Y.S. Kang, J. Stammen J., Ramachandra R., Agnew A.M. et al., "Biomechanical Responses and Injury Assessment of Post Mortem Human Subjects in Various Rear-facing Seating Configurations". Stapp Car Crash J. 2020 Nov;64:155–212. PMID: 33636005.
- [9] Y.S. Kang, G.H. Baker, T. DeWitt, et al., "Thoracic Responses and Injuries of Male Post-Mortem Human Subjects in a Homogeneous Rear-Facing Seat During High-Speed Frontal Impact", Annals of Biomedical Engineering 53, 2025, pp 520–535 doi: 10.1007/s10439-024-03646-2.
- [10] TRC Inc. "Research Consortium for Crashworthiness in Automated Driving Systems (RCCADS)" <https://www.trcpg.com/services/rccads/>, accessed 30.06.2025.
- [11] Material Spec-sheet, "Zote Foams- Plastazote MP15 Low Density Foam", <https://zotefoams.com/wp-content/uploads/2025/03/MP15-December-2017.pdf>, accessed 25.06.2025.
- [12] L. Trummel, A. Keller, "Validation tests of the VIRTUAL open access car seat model, M 3.3 of the H2020 project VIRTUAL", 2020.
- [13] H. Zellmer and F. Manneck, "Assessing Injury Risk of Car Occupants on Rearward Facing Seats in a Full Frontal Impact–Sled Tests in a Generic Test Environment," in 26th ESV conference 2019, Eindhoven, The Netherlands, 19-0201.
- [14] A.V. Ngo, J. Becker, D. Thirunavukkarasu, P. Urban, S. Koetniyom, J. Carmai, "Investigation of occupant kinematics and injury risk in a reclined and rearward-facing seat under various frontal crash velocities." Journal of Safety Research, Volume 79, 2021, pp 26–37, ISSN 0022-4375.
- [15] J. Jobin, C. Klug, M. Kranjec, E. Svenning, J. Iraeus, "Hello, world! VIVA+: A human body model lineup to evaluate sex-differences in crash protection" Frontiers in Bioengineering and Biotechnology, Volume 10:918904, 2022, DOI 10.3389/fbioe.2022.918904.
- [16] Y.S. Kang, T. DeWitt, A. Marcallini, J. Songet et al., "Responses and Injuries of Male Post-Mortem Human subjects (PMHS) Seated in an Unreinforced Production Seat in Rear-facing Frontal Impacts," in IRCOBI conference 2024, Stockholm, pp 161–193.
- [17] Y.S. Kang, V. Pradhan, J. Stammen et al. "Pelvic Responses and Injuries to Male Post-Mortem Human Subjects (PMHS) in Rear-facing Seat Configurations in High-speed Frontal Impacts," in IRCOBI conference 2024, Stockholm, pp. 138–160.
- [18] Z.J. Wang, B. Loeber, A. Tesny, G. Hu, Y.S. Kang "Neck Biofidelity Comparison of THOR-AV, THOR and Hybrid III 50th Dummies," in IRCOBI Conference 2021, pp 136–156.
- [19] National Highway Traffic Safety Administration (NHTSA), Department of Transportation (DOT), "Advance notice of proposed rulemaking - FMVSS 207 Seating Systems", 49 CFR Part 571 Docket No. NHTSA-2024-0001 RIN 2127-AM53.